

The Rare Earths. Part—XCII: Chelating Tendencies of 1-Methoxy-2,4-pentanedione

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Chelating tendencies of 1-methoxy-2,4-pentanedione toward trivalent lanthanide ions were measured in 50% (v/v) dioxane-water media, and thermodynamic formation constants were obtained. In addition, enthalpy values were obtained by thermometric titrations using the same systems. The data obtained support the interpretation of an expanded solvation sphere through the lanthanide series. The use of the mixed solvent system permitted third formation constants to be obtained without concomitant problems of precipitation, although the possibility of dioxane coordination in the solvent sphere exists. Relatively large values of entropy of formation for the overall chelation processes imply an increase in the hydration number from lanthanum through lutetium. Anomalies in chelating tendencies at gadolinium and erbium are difficult to explain unambiguously. The values may indicate a type of cross-over point at which solvent-metal and ligand-metal interactions result in a break in the apparent continuity of the ligand-metal process through the series.

MANY studies of the chelating tendencies of lanthanide ions have involved a single chelating agent associated with a single metal ion, e.g., lanthanide-aminepolycarboxylate chelates and studies of the chelating tendencies of β -diketones have been limited¹ despite the advantages that these systems may offer. The present study was initiated to permit comparison of the effects of oxygen-oxygen coordination versus oxygen-nitrogen coordination, to make a comparison of inductive and steric effects of various substituents (R, R' and R'') in RCOCH(R'')COR' of the β -diketonate chelating agent.

Some experimental difficulties and advantages were anticipated. A mixed-solvent system was required, because of the insolubilities of the metal chelates, $\text{Ln(RCOCH}_2\text{COR')}_3$, in water. The use of dioxane-water systems, however, for obtaining thermodynamic formation constants has been well established¹. In addition, the study of lanthanide-acetylacetonate complexes made by Fernelius and co-workers² indicated that complexes of reasonable stabilities could be obtained.

It was also evident that 1-methoxy-2,4-pentanedione could offer the advantage of reasonable stability plus enhanced solubilities. Finally, the possibility of obtaining three stepwise equilibrium constants was attractive for several obvious reasons.

The use of enthalpy titration data seemed advisable for evaluating ΔH_n , the change in enthalpy associated with a given stepwise chelation process, because the equilibria were established sufficiently rapidly and because data were not available to

permit thermodynamic formation constants to be determined for dioxane-water media at temperatures other than 30°.

Experimental

Materials: 1-Methoxy-2,4-pentanedione from a commercial source was fractionally distilled under vacuum (52°/1 mm Hg), n_D^{20} 1.4590 obs; 1.4590 reported³. Perchlorate solutions: solutions of scandium, yttrium and lanthanide metal perchlorates were prepared from weighed quantities of oxides (99+% purity) by treatment with stoichiometric amounts of perchloric acid (G. F. Smith Chemical Co.; diluted and standardized to 0.1000 M). All perchlorate salt solutions were standardized titrimetrically using xylenolorange as an indicator⁴. The usual precautions were taken in preparing dioxane and water⁵.

Dissociation constants were determined in 50% dioxane-water, using tetramethylammonium hydroxide, as described elsewhere¹.

Formation constants: Titration solutions consisted of 5×10^{-3} M chelating agent and 4×10^{-4} M trivalent metal perchlorate in appropriate dioxane-water solutions to give 50% (v/v) contained in a four-necked titration flask immersed in a bath maintained at $30.00 \pm 0.02^\circ$. The procedure used in the titration is described elsewhere^{1, 5, 6}.

Enthalpy titrations: The enthalpy titration system consisted of five components: (1) a constant-temperature system, a Pyrex ball jar constant-temperature bath contained within a 350-L constant-temperature water bath, which resulted in the inner

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bath being stabilized to within $\pm 0.001^\circ$; (2) a titrant delivery system, which consisted of a Sargent model "C" constant-rate buret; (3) a titration cell, which consisted of a Dewar flask constructed from a 60/50 outer joint with a total volume of about 200 ml; (4) a heating circuit; and (5) a cell-temperature monitor system. Full details are provided elsewhere⁶.

The enthalpy titration involved a continuous-addition technique: a 100.0 ± 0.1 ml sample of metal perchlorate and chelating agent in appropriate solvents (50 vol% dioxane-water) was placed in the cell and, following thermal equilibration, was treated by the continuous addition of titrant (1.0 M KOH). The temperature evolved was recorded on a strip chart as a thermogram, a time-dependent curve which represents the temperature of the calorimeter at any instant of time, relative to the initial temperature. A number of corrections and calibrations were made, including correction for the cooling effect due to entering solvent, calibration of the titration cell, calibration of the strip chart to temperature, evaluation of the heat capacities of the solvents, determination of the heat of ionization of the chelating agent, calculations of concentrations of the species initially and at a given time, t_i , correction of species distributions as a function of ionic strength and, finally, calculation of the enthalpies for the stepwise equilibria. The detailed descriptions of these treatments, together with the computer programs which effect the calculations of the heat of complex-ion formation, are presented elsewhere⁶.

Results

Thermodynamic parameters for 1-methoxy-2,4-pentanedione: Typically, the pK_D value of a β -diketone is a linear function of the mole fraction of dioxane (N_2) in a dioxane-water solution, and the same was true in this study [$pK_D = 7.36 \pm 0.11 + (10.72 \pm 0.43) N_2$]. A polynomial least-squares treatment gives a better fit for the data, but either plot shows the increase in pK_D with a decrease in the dipole moment of the solvent. At $N_2 = 0.173$ (50 vol% dioxane), the values of the thermodynamic constants

are $\Delta G_D^\circ = 13.20 \pm 0.01$ kcal/mole; $\Delta H_D^\circ = 0.99 \pm 0.08$ kcal/mole; and $\Delta S_D^\circ = -40.3 \pm 0.1$ e.u. at $30.0 \pm 0.01^\circ$. These values indicate that ionization of the chelating agent is primarily an entropy controlled process. Since ionization diminishes the entropy of the system, ionization is favored in higher dielectric solvents (lower values of N_2).

Other observations support this contention. Kido and Fernelius⁷ observed little change in $\Delta H_{ionization}$ as a function of N_2 . This and the observations of the present study indicate that the bonding energy differences remain fairly consistent with N_2 .

Several structural implications also result from these parameters. First, the hydrogen ion must form nearly identical aggregations regardless of N_2 in the range studied. Also, the bulk solvent aggregation must be substantially diminished as the mole fraction of dioxane increases. Finally, water molecules remain the principal coordinating solvent species, and the dioxane molecules primarily affect the bulk solution properties. The importance of this view in extrapolating to a metal ion system is evident. Another supporting observation: the heat capacity of 50% (v/v) dioxane-water was determined to be 0.75 cal/ml- $^\circ$ C, whereas the value of pure water is 1.0 cal/ml- $^\circ$ C, at 30° , which is interpreted as indicating less aggregation in the mixed-solvent medium.

Formation constants for selected lanthanide ions in different dioxane-water mixtures:

Thermodynamic formation constants, as $\log K_n$, were evaluated at four different mole fractions of dioxane in dioxane-water mixtures. Pertinent results are listed in Table 1.

An ionic relationship proposed by Born [$\log K = C(1-1/D)$] was tested using the data in Table 1 and deviations from linearity were observed for all plots when N_2 is less than about 0.1, although the degree of non-linearity is not substantial. A substantial deviation in linearity implies that either the metal ion solvation does not remain constant from one solvent system to another or that covalency

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMIC FORMATION CONSTANTS OF La^{3+} , Gd^{3+} and Lu^{3+} -1-METHOXY-2,4-PENTANEDIONE CHELATES AT SELECTED N_2 VALUES AT $30.00 \pm 0.02^\circ$

M^{3+}	N_2	0.0825 (30%) ^b		0.1735 (50%) ^b		0.2805 (65%) ^b		0.3864 (75%) ^b	
		$\log K_f$	R_f^a						
La^{3+}	1	6.191	0.712	7.419	0.779	8.804	0.825	10.004	0.838
	2	4.675	0.537	5.828	0.612	7.267	0.681	8.496	0.711
	3	3.866	0.444	4.662	0.490	5.819	0.545	6.990	0.585
Gd^{3+}	1	7.113	0.818	8.348	0.877	9.678	0.907	11.048	0.925
	2	5.456	0.627	6.595	0.693	8.037	0.753	9.394	0.787
	3	4.206	0.483	4.898	0.515	5.985	0.561	7.329	0.614
Lu^{3+}	1	7.354	0.845	8.536	0.897	9.747	0.912	11.271	0.944
	2	5.715	0.657	6.795	0.714	8.339	0.782	9.614	0.805
	3	4.328	0.497	5.025	0.528	6.326	0.593	7.623	0.638
D_0		51.38		33.85		21.77		14.68	

^a $R_f = \log K_f / pTK_f$.

^b (XX%) represents XX% (volume dioxane)/(volume dioxane + volume water).

^c The symbol D represents the solvent dielectric constant of the solvent system given at the top of the column.

exists in the metal-to-ligand bonding. Considering that the degree of deviation is small, we are led to the conclusion that there may not be a substantial change in the inner coordination sphere of solvated lanthanide ions in dioxane-water mixtures as compared with water as a solvent. The data for $\log K_s$ for gadolinium show a notably linear Born plot; but whether this indicates a remarkably different process in comparison with those for lanthanum or lutetium remains uncertain, considering the small deviation from linearity. These results also indicated that studies using 50% (v/v) dioxane-water would provide results that would be representative of most mixtures (with N_2 above 0.1).

Thermodynamic constants for chelating tendencies of lanthanide ions :

Pertinent data are summarized in Tables 2-4. The results can be considered in order.

The values of ΔG° are plotted in Fig. 1 using the data from Table 2. When this is done, a distinct break appears at gadolinium for the first, second, and perhaps, the third chelation process. Also, such a plot reveals that ΔG° is anomalous for lanthanum; otherwise results are consistent with what others have found for other systems including the observation of a so-called "gadolinium break". In addition, the magnitude of the overall process, ΔG_{1-3} , is similar to the values obtained for other lanthanide complexes, e.g., 25 to 28 kcal/mole for $\text{La}^{3+}-\text{Lu}^{3+}$ versus 22-28 kcal/mole for DCTA complexes^{8,9}. It must be recognized, however, that formation constants of complexes of EDTA and DCTA were determined in 0.1 M KNO_3 , whereas the data for the β -diketone (Table 2) were obtained for 50% dioxane-water.

A similar problem occurs when the chelating tendencies of 1-methoxy-2,4-pentanedione toward lanthanide metal ions are compared with those of 2,4-pentanedione. The former were evaluated for 50% dioxane-water and the latter^{2a} for dilute aqueous solutions at an ionic strength of 0.1. The available data clearly show the greater stabilities of the 1-methoxy-2,4-pentanedione complexes ($\log \beta_3 =$

Fig. 1. Gibbs free energy of formation, ΔG° , Kcal/mole, as a function of atomic number, Z, for 1-methoxy-2,4-pentanedione chelates of the lanthanides. The value of i is 1 for \circ , 2 for \bullet and 3 for \odot . The position of yttrium in the series is indicated by the symbol \cdot . The size of the circles approximates the standard deviation of the value.

$\log \beta_3 = ca 11-12$)^{2a}. A more reasonable comparison may result if the pK_D values are compared: the values for $N_2=0.173$ are 10.37 for 2,4-pentanedione¹⁰ and 9.52 for 1-methoxy-2,4-pentanedione. If the values of $\log K$ parallel the pK_D values for closely related β -diketones as has been observed previously¹¹, then the complexes of 2,4-pentanedione should be somewhat more stable than those of 1-methoxy-2,4-pentanedione.

TABLE 2—FREE ENERGY OF FORMATION OF Ln^{3+} -1-METHOXY-2,4-PENTANEDIONE CHELATES IN 50.0 (v/v) % DIOXANE-WATER MEDIUM AT $30.00 \pm 0.01^\circ$

Z	M ³⁺	$-\Delta G^\circ_1$ Kcal/mole	$-\Delta G^\circ_2$ Kcal/mole	$-\Delta G^\circ_3$ Kcal/mole	$-\Delta G^\circ_{1,2}$ Kcal/mole	$-\Delta G^\circ_{1,3}$ Kcal/mole
39	Y ³⁺	11.62 ± 0.02 ^a	9.16 ± 0.01	6.74 ± 0.03	20.78 ± 0.03	27.52 ± 0.04
57	La ³⁺	10.28 ± 0.01	8.07 ± 0.05	6.40 ± 0.13	18.35 ± 0.05	24.75 ± 0.14
58	Ce ³⁺	10.59 ± 0.02	8.58 ± 0.06	6.90 ± 0.15	19.17 ± 0.06	26.07 ± 0.16
59	Pr ³⁺	10.71 ± 0.04	8.81 ± 0.05	6.90 ± 0.20	19.53 ± 0.06	26.43 ± 0.21
60	Nd ³⁺	10.86 ± 0.04	8.97 ± 0.05	7.00 ± 0.17	19.83 ± 0.07	26.83 ± 0.19
62	Sm ³⁺	11.37 ± 0.02	9.17 ± 0.02	6.85 ± 0.09	20.55 ± 0.03	27.40 ± 0.10
63	Eu ³⁺	11.50 ± 0.07	9.29 ± 0.01	6.96 ± 0.04	20.79 ± 0.07	27.75 ± 0.08
64	Gd ³⁺	11.52 ± 0.02	9.13 ± 0.01	6.78 ± 0.03	20.65 ± 0.02	27.43 ± 0.03
65	Tb ³⁺	11.67 ± 0.02	9.27 ± 0.01	6.87 ± 0.02	20.94 ± 0.02	27.80 ± 0.03
66	Dy ³⁺	11.69 ± 0.02	9.22 ± 0.01	6.78 ± 0.02	20.91 ± 0.02	27.69 ± 0.03
67	Ho ³⁺	11.69 ± 0.02	9.24 ± 0.01	6.83 ± 0.10	20.93 ± 0.03	27.76 ± 0.10
68	Er ³⁺	11.72 ± 0.02	9.26 ± 0.01	6.83 ± 0.02	20.98 ± 0.02	27.81 ± 0.03
69	Tm ³⁺	11.76 ± 0.02	9.33 ± 0.01	6.92 ± 0.03	21.09 ± 0.02	28.01 ± 0.03
70	Yb ³⁺	11.82 ± 0.02	9.40 ± 0.01	6.91 ± 0.01	21.22 ± 0.02	28.13 ± 0.02
71	Lu ³⁺	11.79 ± 0.03	9.44 ± 0.01	7.04 ± 0.02	21.23 ± 0.03	28.28 ± 0.03

^a Standard deviation of value.

TABLE 3—ENTHALPY OF FORMATION OF Ln^{3+} -1-METHOXY-2,4-PENTANEDIONE CHELATES IN 50.0 (v/v) % DIOXANE-WATER MEDIUM AT $30.00 \pm 0.01^\circ$

Z	M ³⁺	ΔH_1° Kcal/mole	ΔH_2° Kcal/mole	ΔH_3° Kcal/mole	$\Delta H_{1,2}^\circ$ Kcal/mole	$\Delta H_{1,3}^\circ$ Kcal/mole
39	Y ³⁺	2.03 ± 0.6^a	-2.89 ± 1.0	-0.46 ± 0.8	0.86 ± 1.2	-1.32 ± 1.4
57	La ³⁺	2.25 ± 0.2	-1.85 ± 0.4	-3.39 ± 1.1	0.40 ± 0.4	-3.00 ± 1.2
58	Ce ³⁺	2.31 ± 0.1	-3.36 ± 0.7	-1.23 ± 2.0	-1.05 ± 0.7	-2.28 ± 2.1
59	Pr ³⁺	2.38 ± 0.1	-3.66 ± 0.5	-1.34 ± 1.3	-1.28 ± 0.5	-2.62 ± 1.4
60	Nd ³⁺	1.69 ± 0.2	-2.73 ± 0.5	-2.12 ± 1.3	-1.04 ± 0.6	-3.16 ± 1.4
62	Sm ³⁺	0.58 ± 0.1	-0.76 ± 0.5	-4.14 ± 1.5	-0.19 ± 0.5	-4.33 ± 1.5
63	Eu ³⁺	2.61 ± 0.3	-2.82 ± 0.5	-2.51 ± 0.7	-0.21 ± 0.6	-2.72 ± 1.0
64	Gd ³⁺	2.75 ± 0.4	-0.35 ± 0.7	-4.00 ± 0.6	2.40 ± 0.8	-1.61 ± 1.0
65	Tb ³⁺	0.93 ± 0.5	-1.78 ± 1.0	-0.58 ± 0.8	-0.84 ± 1.1	-1.42 ± 1.4
66	Dy ³⁺	2.39 ± 0.3	-2.79 ± 0.6	-1.39 ± 0.5	0.40 ± 0.7	-1.79 ± 0.9
67	Ho ³⁺	2.60 ± 0.2	-3.26 ± 0.3	-0.62 ± 0.3	-0.66 ± 0.3	-1.28 ± 0.4
68	Er ³⁺	-0.69 ± 0.2	3.77 ± 0.6	-6.07 ± 1.0	3.08 ± 0.6	-2.99 ± 1.2
69	Tm ³⁺	-0.14 ± 0.5	1.18 ± 0.9	-1.64 ± 0.7	1.04 ± 1.0	-0.60 ± 1.2
70	Yb ³⁺	1.42 ± 0.5	0.10 ± 0.9	-0.92 ± 0.8	1.52 ± 1.0	0.60 ± 1.3
71	Lu ³⁺	-0.99 ± 0.4	2.63 ± 0.8	-2.32 ± 0.7	1.64 ± 0.9	-0.68 ± 1.1

^a Standard deviation of the value.TABLE 4—ENTROPY OF FORMATION OF Ln^{3+} -1-METHOXY-2,4-PENTANEDIONE CHELATES IN 50.0 (v/v) % DIOXANE-WATER MEDIUM AT $30.00 \pm 0.01^\circ$

Z	M ³⁺	ΔS_1° E. U.	ΔS_2° E. U.	ΔS_3° E. U.	$\Delta S_{1,2}^\circ$ E. U.	$\Delta S_{1,3}^\circ$ E. U.
39	Y ³⁺	45.0 ± 1.8^a	20.7 ± 3.3	20.7 ± 2.6	65.7 ± 3.8	86.4 ± 4.6
57	La ³⁺	41.3 ± 0.5	20.5 ± 1.3	9.9 ± 3.6	61.8 ± 1.4	71.8 ± 3.9
58	Ce ³⁺	42.6 ± 0.4	17.2 ± 2.1	18.7 ± 6.1	59.8 ± 2.1	78.5 ± 6.5
59	Pr ³⁺	43.2 ± 0.3	17.0 ± 1.6	18.4 ± 4.2	60.2 ± 1.6	78.5 ± 4.5
60	Nd ³⁺	41.4 ± 0.7	20.6 ± 1.7	16.1 ± 4.2	62.0 ± 1.8	78.1 ± 4.6
62	Sm ³⁺	39.4 ± 0.4	27.7 ± 1.6	8.9 ± 4.7	67.2 ± 1.6	76.1 ± 4.9
63	Eu ³⁺	46.6 ± 0.9	21.3 ± 1.9	14.7 ± 2.2	67.9 ± 2.1	82.5 ± 3.1
64	Gd ³⁺	47.1 ± 1.2	28.9 ± 2.2	9.2 ± 2.0	76.0 ± 2.5	85.2 ± 3.1
65	Tb ³⁺	41.6 ± 1.7	24.7 ± 3.2	20.7 ± 2.5	66.3 ± 3.6	87.0 ± 4.4
66	Dy ³⁺	46.4 ± 1.0	21.2 ± 1.9	17.8 ± 1.6	67.7 ± 2.2	85.4 ± 2.7
67	Ho ³⁺	47.1 ± 0.5	19.7 ± 0.9	20.5 ± 0.9	66.9 ± 1.1	87.3 ± 1.4
68	Er ³⁺	36.4 ± 0.7	43.0 ± 1.8	2.5 ± 3.3	79.4 ± 1.9	81.9 ± 3.8
69	Tm ³⁺	38.3 ± 1.6	34.7 ± 2.8	17.4 ± 2.2	73.0 ± 3.2	90.4 ± 3.9
70	Yb ³⁺	43.7 ± 1.5	31.3 ± 2.8	19.8 ± 2.5	75.0 ± 3.2	94.8 ± 4.1
71	Lu ³⁺	35.6 ± 1.4	39.8 ± 2.5	15.6 ± 2.3	75.5 ± 2.8	91.0 ± 2.8

^a Standard deviation of the value.

Changes in the enthalpy and entropy of complex formation when plotted as a function of atomic number of trivalent lanthanide show a complex pattern, Fig. 2-4. The values for ΔH_1° and ΔH_2° decrease from Z=57 to 71 with notable breaks (minima) at Z=62-63, 64-65 and 68. The values of ΔH_3° show, in contrast, a general increase from Z=57-71 with notable deviations at Z=63 (minimum) and 68 (maximum). The significant common feature is the direct relationship between the change in enthalpy and change in entropy. Both tend to show parallel increases in the variations with atomic number of the lanthanide metal ion.

The latter observation is worth stressing that an interpretation may be made in terms of the structure of the reacting species.

Discussion

This study was the first application of a continuous addition technique to a lanthanide-ligand system in a mixed solvent system which permitted truly thermodynamic constants to be obtained. Although incremental addition techniques may be more accurate, the continuous addition technique affords the advantages of rapidity and convenience.

The chief problems, apart from experimental design, were the computations of species distributions as a function of addition of titrant. These were solved through the aid of appropriate programs for high-speed computers⁵.

The data presented here support an interpretation of an expanded solvation sphere through the lanthanide series. The nature of the solvation sphere is open to interpretation, owing to the mixed solvent system used, but it appears that dioxane has a greater role in the deaggregation of water molecules than as an actual solvation participant. Data obtained in this study, together with the data obtained by Kido and Fernelius⁷, amply support this view.

Anomalies in chelating tendencies at gadolinium and at erbium are still difficult to explain in an unambiguous manner. The anomalies may constitute a type of cross-over point at which the variations in solvent-metal and ligand-metal interactions result in a break in the ligand metal bonding process through the series. For example, if the β -diketone changes from terdentate to bidentate near gadolinium and erbium in the lanthanide series, then the observed entropy anomaly would be understandable: a

Fig. 2. Thermodynamic parameters, ΔG°_1 , \circ , Kcal/mole ; ΔH°_1 , \bullet , Kcal/mole ; and ΔS°_1 , \ominus , E. U., as a function of atomic number, Z, for the first step of chelate formation for the lanthanide-1-methoxy-2,4-pentanedione system. If the standard deviation of the value exceeds the representative circle, it is indicated by a vertical bar. The position of yttrium in the series is represented by the symbol Δ .

decrease in the entropy of chelation should result in a decrease in the enthalpy of chelation in as much as the bond not formed would involve the other oxygen atom of the ligand. There is evidence for this type of non-involvement in the complexes of lanthanides with pyrimidone¹². With this system, chelation involves an amine nitrogen atom plus one ring nitrogen atom both, not the other. The second ring nitrogen atom presumably does not bond for steric reasons ; the effect of solvent system was implied though not delineated¹².

Possibly, higher coordination or solvation must be invoked to account for the small differences in the chelating tendencies of 1-methoxy-2,4-pentanedionate with trivalent lanthanides. If a solvent species is not held tenaciously in the second or third solvation spheres, the removal of this species should have less impact on macrochemical observations (e.g., formation constant, change in entropy, change in enthalpy) than the removal of the same solvent species from the first coordination sphere. The logic of this statement derives from the fact that ΔG° , ΔS° and ΔH° are state functions that are subject to time averaging if a rapid exchange in the initial and final states exists. A more labile species possesses more energy (S° initial) and is held less tenaciously (less H° initial) ; thus the overall-state functions ΔG° , ΔS° and ΔH° of chelation are less affected

Fig. 3. Thermodynamic parameters, $\Delta G^{\circ}_{1,2}$, \bullet , Kcal/mole ; $\Delta H^{\circ}_{1,2}$, \ominus , Kcal/mole ; and $\Delta S^{\circ}_{1,2}$, \circ , E. U., as a function of atomic number, Z, for the first and second steps of chelate formation for the lanthanide-1-methoxy-2,4-pentanedione system. If the standard deviation of the value exceeds the size of the representative circle, it is indicated by a vertical bar. The position of yttrium in the series is represented by the symbol Δ .

ted by species in the second and third solvation spheres than those in the first sphere.

The results of this study, more specifically, are consistent with two processes (1) a decrease in the first solvation sphere around gadolinium and (2) an increased solvation of other lanthanide ions. The former process has been proposed and supported by Hoard¹³ and by Grenthe¹⁴ ; the second by Padova¹⁵. The hypothesis that the coordination sphere is drastically disrupted by the first chelation process is supported by large values of ΔS_1 and the large positive values of ΔH_1 .

The final delineation of the solution structure of lanthanide ions may be completed through the use of several methods. Investigation of activity data for these ions in various solvents offers promise¹⁶. Another approach may be the use of radiation diffraction techniques in very concentrated solutions¹⁷. In any event, equilibrium data will contribute to the ultimate solution of the gadolinium break by pointing the way to more structurally oriented techniques. The fact that the observations made in this study support prevalent theories of coordination number change suggests that the true

Fig. 4. Thermodynamic parameters, $\Delta G^{\circ}_{1,2,3}$, \bullet , Kcal/mole; $\Delta H^{\circ}_{1,2,3}$, \circ , Kcal/mole; $\Delta S^{\circ}_{1,2,3}$, \circ , E. U., as a function of atomic number, Z , for the first, second and third steps of chelate formation for the lanthanide-1-methoxy-2,4-pentanedione system. If the standard deviation of the value exceeds the size of the representative circle, it is indicated by a vertical bar. The position of yttrium in the series is represented by the symbol Δ .

interpretation is probably a synthesis of the two. The method used in this study is shown to be valid for a solvent system other than water, and for this the thermodynamic properties of the lanthanides may be investigated in a variety of closely related solvent systems with varying dielectric constants. This approach should permit the ultimate evaluation of the activity data needed to infer structural characteristics.

Ultimately, the problem of the gadolinium break and other apparent anomalies may be more a problem of the structure of water than a problem of the exact coordination tendencies of the lanthanides.

This possibility awaits the investigations of systems that involve much less hydrogen bonding and that are less polar than water. The present study indicated the direction and some of the methods that these studies may take.

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